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Abstract

Challenges in Combining Historical and Cartographical Sources in a Historical GIS Project

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“HistoGIS” is an open source Geographic Information System, workbench and repository of historical spatial data sets developed and curated by a team of researchers at the Austrian Center for Digital Humanities (Austrian Academy of Sciences). [1]

The project is dedicated to collecting, georeferencing and vectorising digitized historical maps of 19th Century Europe and combining these shapefiles with historical legal data on border lines. Moreover, “HistoGIS” intends to collect and curate already existing data sets provided by other projects (e.g. the Census Mosaic [2]) and complement these data sets with our own additional information. The resulting temporalized shapefiles aim to make the shifting extent of political entities, a result of border changes that occurred in this period, visible and enable further spatial queries and analyses. We are currently working on data on the German unification, Austrian and Austro-Hungarian administrative reforms, and European border changes on a national level, between 1815 and c. 1920. All data sets are made publicly available through the HistoGIS web application.

This paper addresses three main challenges that the project faces in regard to its source material. First, given the intentional and unintentional inaccuracies present in historical maps, the conflict arises between accurately representing the sources (maps), or striving towards accurately representing reality. Second, due to these inaccuracies, maps from different sources don't fit with each other. Hence, different vectorized map layers often do not lie exactly on top of each other and borders are slightly shifted. This might result in confusing representations and intensifies the data accuracy issue. Third, not every border change that can be found in legal sources (laws, international treaties, etc.), especially on district level, is represented in available maps. This raises the question of how to successfully combine comparatively detailed historical legal data with imprecise and fragmentary historical spatial data.

[1] <https://histogis.acdh.oeaw.ac.at/>; <https://github.com/acdh-oeaw/histogis>

[2] Census Mosaic Project funded by the Austrian Science Fund (FWF), Project Number P 21157